

Polarographic Studies of Tl^+ and Pb^{2+} Complexes of L-Lysine Monohydrochloride

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Manuscript received 24 August 1982, revised 22 February 1983, accepted 28 April 1983

Complexation of Tl^+ and Pb^{2+} with L-lysine monohydrochloride has been studied polarographically. The reduction of Tl^+ and Pb^{2+} in lysine media at d.m.e. in presence of $0.1 M NaClO_4$ and 0.002% Triton-X-100 has been found to be reversible and diffusion controlled. The plots of $-E_{1/2}$ vs $-\log[Lys]$ reveal the formation of metal-lysine complexes viz., 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 for Tl^+ and 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 for Pb^{2+} at pH 8.0 and 4.0, respectively. The stability constants of these complexes have been determined at 30 and 40° employing DeFord and Hume's method and Mihailov's mathematical approach. The thermodynamic parameters ΔG , ΔH and ΔS accompanying the complexation reactions have also been evaluated at 30°.

AMINO acids containing active $-NH_2$ and $-COOH$ groups have several useful applications in biological, medicinal and allied fields and are well known for the formation of complexes with metals. The polarographic behaviour of several amino acids and their metal complexes have been studied by Saxena and coworkers¹⁻⁴ and yielded useful results. In this communication, the complexation of L-lysine monohydrochloride with $Tl(I)$ and $Pb(II)$ has been studied polarographically. The composition and stability constants of these complexes have been determined at 30 and 40° employing DeFord and Hume's method and refined treatment of Mihailov's mathematical approach. The overall changes in thermodynamic parameters ΔG , ΔH and ΔS have also been evaluated at 30°.

Experimental

L-Lysine monohydrochloride (referred as Lys) and all other chemicals were guaranteed reagents. A Cambridge general purpose polarograph with scalamp galvanometer and SCE as reference electrode in conjunction with a thermostated 'H' cell was used for recording the polarograms. The characteristic of the capillary in $0.1 M NaClO_4$ at 0.4 volts vs SCE with h_{Hg} 50 cm was $m=2.953$ mg/sec, $t=3.5$ sec/drop, $m^{2/3}t^{1/6}=2.536$ $mg^{2/3}S^{1/6}$.

The polarograms of the solutions containing $1 mM M^{n+}$ (M^{n+} represents Tl^+ or Pb^{2+} ion) and different concentration of lysine in presence of $0.1 M NaClO_4$ as supporting electrolyte and 0.002% Triton-X-100 as maximum suppressor, were recorded at pH 8.0 and 4.0, respectively in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen.

Results and Discussion

The polarograms of Tl^+ -Lys system and Pb^{2+} -Lys system at d.m.e. yield single well defined

cathodic waves at pH 8.0 and 4.0, respectively. Constancy of i_d/\sqrt{h} indicates the diffusion controlled nature of the reduction wave in both the systems.

The plot $\log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$ vs $-E_{d.e.}$ (V) yielded straight lines with slopes of 0.059 ± 0.005 in the case of Tl^+ and 0.029 ± 0.002 in the case of Pb^{2+} indicating the reversibility of the electrode reaction involving one electron and two electron transfer processes, respectively. The number of electrons involved in the above reduction processes was confirmed by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon.

The half-wave potentials shift towards more negative value with increasing lysine concentration, indicating complexation of Tl^+ and Pb^{2+} with lysine.

A plot of $-E_{1/2}$ as a function of $-\log[Lys]$ showed the curvature indicative of the formation of successive complexes (Figs. 1 and 1') and hence

Fig. 1. Plot of $-E_{1/2}$ vs $-\log C_x$ at 30° for Tl^+ -lysine system.

Fig. 1'. Plot of $-E_{1/2}$ vs $-\log C_X$ for Pb^{2+} -Lys system at 80° .

DeFord and Hume's method was employed for determining various functions $F_j(X)$ defined as

$$F_0(X) = \text{antilog} \left\{ 0.435 \frac{nF}{RT} [(E_{1/2})_S^0 - (E_{1/2})_C] + \log \frac{I_S}{I_C} \right\}$$

$$= 1 + \beta_1(X) + \beta_2(X)^2 + \dots + \beta_n(X)^n$$

$$F_1(X) = \frac{F_0(X) - 1}{C_X} = \beta_1 + \beta_2(X) + \beta_3(X)^2 + \dots + \beta_n(X)^{n-1}$$

$$F_2(X) = \frac{F_1(X) - K_1}{C_X} = \beta_2 + \beta_3(X) + \dots + \beta_n(X)^{n-2}$$

$$F_3(X) = \frac{F_2(X) - K_2}{C_X} = \beta_3 + \beta_4(X) + \dots + \beta_n(X)^{n-3}$$

and so on.

$(E_{1/2})_S^0$ and $(E_{1/2})_C^0$ are the half-wave potentials for the uncomplexed and complexed metal ions, respectively and I_S and I_C are the experimentally determined diffusion currents for these species. The graphical extrapolation of the complexity functions $F_j(X)$ reduces the above equation, which is polynomial in (X) , to n -equations from which corresponding K_{stab} values are obtained. Figs. 2 and 2' show the plot of $F_0(X)$, $F_1(X)$, $F_2(X)$ and $F_3(X)$ vs ligand concentration. Extrapolation of these curves at $C_X=0$ gave values of formation constants which are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

The plots of $F_2(X)$ vs C_X in case of Tl^+ -Lys system and $F_3(X)$ vs C_X in case of Pb^{2+} -Lys system yielded straight lines parallel to C_X -axis which indicates the formation of two complexes of lysine with thallium viz., TlA and TlA_2^+ and three complexes of lysine with lead viz., PbA , PbA_2^+ and PbA_3^{2+} , respectively.

Mihailov's mathematical approach has also been applied for calculating the stability constants from

the relation

$$\beta_n = A \cdot \frac{a^n}{n!}$$

Fig. 2. Plot of $F(X)$ functions vs C_X at 90° for Tl^+ -Lys system.

Fig. 2'. Plots of $F_j(X)$ vs C_X of Pb^{2+} -Lys system at 90° .

the relation $\beta_n = A \cdot \frac{a^n}{n!}$

where a and A are Mihailov's constants whose values can be obtained by solving the following sets of equations:

$$(F' - 1) \sum_1^n \frac{[X']^n}{n!} a^{n-1} - (F'' - 1) \sum_1^n \frac{[X']^n}{n!} a^{n-1} = 0$$

and

$$A = \frac{(F' - 1)}{\sum_1^n \frac{a^n}{n!} [X]^n}$$

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC DATA OF Tl⁺-Lys SYSTEMS ; [C_{Tl⁺}]=1×10⁻⁵ M

Conc. of ligand M	i _d (μA)		-E _{1/2} (V)		F ₀ (X)		F ₁ (X)		F ₂ (X)	
	30°	40°	30°	40°	30°	40°	30°	40°	30°	40°
0	7.2	7.8	0.475	0.473	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.005	7.0	7.5	0.48	0.477	1.246	1.206	49.2	41.31	1140.0	862.0
0.01	6.8	7.4	0.485	0.482	1.553	1.472	55.39	47.23	1189.3	1023.0
0.02	6.6	7.3	0.495	0.492	2.349	2.163	67.48	58.19	1199.0	1059.5
0.03	6.25	7.0	0.503	0.50	3.372	3.037	79.08	67.9	1186.1	1030.2
0.05	6.1	6.85	0.518	0.515	6.14	5.417	102.87	88.35	1187.4	1027.0

 TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC DATA OF Pb²⁺-Lys SYSTEM ; [C_{Pb²⁺}]=1 mM

Conc. of ligand M	i _d (μA)		-E _{1/2} (V)		F ₀ (X)		F ₁ (X)×10		F ₂ (X)10 ²		F ₃ (X)×10 ³	
	30°	40°	30°	40°	30°	40°	30°	40°	30°	40°	30°	40°
0	7.5	7.9	0.398	0.396	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.004	7.2	7.5	0.4025	0.40	1.47	1.42	11.77	10.44	6.94	6.11	9.85	9.02
0.006	7.1	7.4	0.405	0.403	1.87	1.73	13.46	12.16	7.42	6.95	7.38	7.44
0.008	7.0	7.3	0.408	0.406	2.31	2.27	16.35	15.93	9.81	8.66	8.51	7.70
0.01	7.0	7.2	0.411	0.409	3.32	2.88	21.36	18.82	12.36	10.82	9.36	8.32
0.012	6.9	7.2	0.415	0.413	4.005	3.37	25.05	23.98	13.37	13.32	8.64	9.02

TABLE 3—STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS AT 30°

Composition of complex	log K				-ΔG (kcal/mole)	-ΔH (kcal/mole)	ΔS (cal/deg/mole)
	30°		40°				
	X	Y	X	Y			
Tl-Lys							
1:1	1.638	1.637	1.568	1.547	2.37	3.49	-4.04
1:2	3.073	3.075	3.011	3.019	4.4	2.56	8.44
Pb-Lys							
1:1	1.954	1.874	1.903	1.769	2.65	3.38	-2.41
1:2	3.477	3.908	3.397	3.371	5.12	2.52	8.58
1:3	5.939	5.865	5.903	5.797	8.18	2.16	19.86

where F' and F'' are the experimental F functions at ligand concentrations [X'] and [X''], respectively. The values of β_n so obtained for Tl⁺- and Pb²⁺-Lys systems are recorded in Table 3.

The percentage distribution of thallium and lead present in various forms as a function of log [Lys] is obtained from the relation

$$\frac{[M]}{C_M} = \frac{1}{F_0(X)} = \text{fraction present as simple metal ion and}$$

$$\alpha_j = \frac{\beta_j(X)^j}{F_0(X)} = \text{fraction present as complexed } MX_j.$$

The distribution curves are shown in Fig. 3 (for Tl⁺-Lys system).

Thermodynamic functions: The values of ΔG, ΔH and ΔS accompanying the complexation reactions have been evaluated at 30° by employing Gibb's Helmholtz and isobar equations⁷ and are recorded in Table 3.

The results reveal (Table 3) that the stability constant values decrease with rise in temperature. This indicates that lower temperature is favourable for the formation of complexes. The negative

Fig. 3. Distribution curves at 30°. (o) [M], (o) [MX₁], (x) [MX₂]

values of ΔG and ΔH show that the complexation reaction tends to proceed spontaneously and that it

is an exothermic process. This also explains the decrease in the value of $\log K$ with rise in temperature. The overall entropy change being positive for Tl- and Pb-Lys systems favours the formation of complexes.

The present investigation shows the formation of two complexes in case of Tl^+ and three complexes in case of Pb^{2+} with L-lysine monohydrochloride.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi for a Fellowship to one of them (S.K.D.).

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